

**Politecnico
di Torino**

PoliTO's Action Plan for CoARA Progress Report - 2026

CoARA
Coalition for Advancing
Research Assessment

Action Plan 2022–2027: Monitoring of Activities 2025

One year after the publication of the roadmap, the first systematic monitoring of the actions envisaged in the Action Plan was launched, with the aim of assessing their state of progress and the outcomes achieved, while highlighting any critical issues where present.

For each action, the monitoring is structured in tables that report:

- the CoARA supporting commitments to which the action is linked, as well as the key reference commitments;
- the description of the action;
- the implementation timeframe, referring either to the duration of the Agreement (2022–2027) or to a periodic schedule;
- the responsible roles and the organizational units involved in the implementation;
- the connection with the objectives of the University Strategic Plan and with the intervention areas of the University Action Plan, specified through dedicated tags;
- a summary of the progress of the action one year after publication.

This approach strengthens the traceability of actions, the monitoring of progress, and the integration of the CoARA Action Plan into the University's planning, programming, and evaluation processes.

Supporting CoARA Commitment: 6. Review and develop research assessment criteria, tools and processes (individual level)

Action	A.1 Implementation, within recruitment and career progression calls, of a more holistic and inclusive evaluation of applications
Timeline	2025-2027
Indicators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Revision of calls · Impact analysis
Responsibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Vice Rector for Internal Affairs
Other Vice-Rectors Involved	-
Other Structures Involved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · PEPS Department - People, HR Planning and Development · Open Science Study Centre · Centre for Gender Studies
Polito in transition (Rector's Programme)	Objectives: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Improvement of the study and working environment · Care and enhancement of staff Actions: 114, 75, 19, 61, 112
Strategic Plan TAGs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · International University · University as a driver of competitiveness
University Action Plan TAGs - Areas of Intervention	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Enhancement of the vocations of researchers and teaching staff · Career opportunities for early-career researchers
Outcome of the Action	<p>The action is aimed at strengthening the adoption of a more holistic and inclusive approach in the evaluation of applications within recruitment and career progression calls. The changes introduced are intended to ensure a more comprehensive assessment of candidates' profiles, moving beyond an exclusively quantitative reading of the curriculum vitae and enhancing the plurality of professional, scientific, and institutional contributions.</p> <p>In particular, regulations and calls (for RTD positions) have been revised and expanded in order to specify and broaden the range of assessable qualifications, including, among others, participation in spin-offs, commercial projects, research projects, and professional activities. In addition, new categories have been introduced to assess service activities, dissemination, and public engagement. A key feature of the intervention is the introduction of three narrative CV components, one for each of the University's missions, through which candidates can describe in textual form their most significant contribution in the areas of teaching (or self-training), research, and dissemination and service to the community, with particular attention to innovative, experiential, and collaborative teaching practices.</p> <p>To support the effective implementation of this new evaluation approach, specific initiatives are planned for selection committees, with the aim of guiding them to consider the full range of submitted qualifications in a balanced way, including less traditional ones. The adoption of broader and more qualitative evaluation criteria is also consistent with the University's research profile, as highlighted by the results of the Politecnico di Torino in the THE Interdisciplinary Science Rankings, which recognize the institution's capacity to promote and support interdisciplinary and multidisciplinary research activities. This evidence reinforces the relevance of an evaluation approach aimed at enhancing complex, collaborative, and cross-cutting contributions that cannot be adequately represented by exclusively quantitative metrics.</p> <p>In line with this approach, the University has institutional measures and tools that support and make visible the outcomes of interdisciplinary research, as well as dedicated organizational and administrative infrastructures. In particular, information and indicators are available on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · research results (https://www.polito.it/en/research/results) · interdepartmental structures and centres supporting interdisciplinary research teams (https://www.polito.it/en/research/ecosystem/interdepartmental-centers) · administrative services dedicated to research management (https://www.polito.it/en/polito/about-us/administration?cod_struttura=S6517N) · recruitment and career progression procedures that allow recognition and enhancement of interdisciplinary contributions (https://www.polito.it/en/polito/work-with-us/working-in-research/direct-recruitment-of-full-and-associate-professors) <p>These elements strengthen the coherence of the action with the University's scientific profile and with the objective of an evaluation system capable of recognizing complex and collaborative contributions.</p>

Supporting CoARA Commitment: 6. Review and develop research assessment criteria, tools and processes (individual level)

Action	<p>A.2 Revision of internal evaluation and incentive criteria for PhD candidates in relation to core commitments 1, 2, and 3</p>
Timeline	2025
Indicators	-
Responsibility	Director of the Doctoral School (ScuDo)
Other Vice-Rectors Involved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Vice Rector for Scientific and Technological Innovation · Vice Rector for Education · Vice Rector for PoliTo Strategic Plan · Vice Rector for Equal Opportunities, Inclusiveness and Life Quality · Vice Rector for Society and Public Engagement, Community, and Rector’s Program Implementation
Other Structures Involved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Ph.D. programmes and Postgraduate School · PEPS Department - People, HR Planning and Development · PoliTO Strategies Study Center · Centre for Gender Studies
Politointransition (Rector’s Programme)	<p>Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Improvement of the study and working environment · Care and enhancement of staff <p>Actions: 1 14, 75, 19, 61, 112</p>
Strategic Plan TAGs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · International University; · University as a driver of competitiveness
University Action Plan TAGs - Areas of Intervention	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Enhancement of the vocations of researchers and teaching staff · Career opportunities for early-career researchers
Outcome of the Action	<p>In 2025, a revision of the criteria for the evaluation of PhD candidates’ publications was initiated. In addition, a document prepared by the Director of the Doctoral School, dedicated to the future strategies of the Politecnico di Torino regarding doctoral education, is currently under discussion within the University’s governing bodies.</p> <p>This document is inspired by the Salzburg Principles and reiterates that evaluation criteria should be qualitative and not based solely on numerical indicators. Such indicators are used to verify minimum requirements that each PhD candidate must meet (e.g., minimum number of publications, consistency of training activities), while evaluation for annual progression and admission to the final examination is based, across all programmes, on the discussion of research results with the academic board. In particular, metrics related to citations and journal impact factors are not used directly.</p> <p>The Doctoral School annually awards quality prizes to PhD candidates who demonstrate particularly high performance. In this case as well, evaluation—entrusted to the individual doctoral boards—is carried out by considering all the activities undertaken during the programme, including third mission activities, which the University is in the process of systematically mapping.</p> <p>To define the final ranking, some doctoral programmes also use peer review mechanisms applied to materials produced by candidates (e.g., videos, presentations).</p> <p>In 2026, the University intends to complete the approval process of its doctoral education strategies, as well as the revision of the evaluation criteria for PhD candidates’ publications.</p>

Supporting CoARA Commitment: 6. Review and develop research assessment criteria, tools and processes (individual level)

Action	A.3 Definition of criteria for the evaluation of research within departmental structures
Timeline	Ongoing
Indicators	-
Responsibility	Rector
Other Vice-Rectors Involved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Vice Rector for PoliTo Strategic Plan · Vice Rector for Quality Assurance · Vice Rector for Human and Economic Resources · Vice Rector for Equal Opportunities, Inclusiveness and Life Quality · Vice Rector for Society and Public Engagement, Community, and Rector's Program Implementation
Other Structures Involved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · PoliTO Strategies Study Center · Centre for Gender Studies · STARQ Office in staff to the Director General - Strategy, Analysis, Reporting and Quality
Polito in transition (Rector's Programme)	<p>Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Enhancement of research environments · Strengthening of research support · Promotion of internationally oriented research <p>Actions: 69, 75, 86, 107, 108, 121</p>
Strategic Plan TAGs	International University
University Action Plan TAGs - Areas of Intervention	Enhancement of the vocations of researchers and teaching staff
Outcome of the Action	<p>The Action is framed within the new model of Departmental Strategic Planning (PSD), which introduces a structured framework for the definition, monitoring, and evaluation of departmental activities, including those related to research. Each Department is required to develop its own PSD through departmental projects aligned with the objectives of the University Strategic Plan.</p> <p>These projects form the basis for the allocation of a share of resources and include the identification of indicators to assess the achievement of objectives. Such indicators are defined by the Departments in agreement with the University, ensuring autonomy in the selection of evaluation criteria while maintaining strategic coherence and compliance with the regulatory framework.</p> <p>The model предусматривает an ex ante evaluation of projects, in terms of strategic coherence and level of ambition, carried out by the Evaluation Unit, and an ex post evaluation based on the annual monitoring of the identified parameters, also supported by centrally provided indicators. Monitoring supports review, reporting, and resource allocation processes at both departmental and university governance levels.</p> <p>Each Department is also required to define its own criteria for resource distribution, to be specified in a dedicated section of the PSD. In this context, the definition of research evaluation criteria at the departmental level takes the form of a structured process based on explicit objectives, projects, and shared indicators, strengthening the link between planning, evaluation, and decision-making processes, in line with the principles promoted by CoARA.</p>

Supporting CoARA Commitment: 6. Review and develop research assessment criteria, tools and processes (individual level)

Action	A.4 Review of the University's bibliometric criteria in relation to the core commitments of the Agreement.
Timeline	2025-2027
Indicators	Summary document of the study results.
Responsibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Rector's Representative for the Research Quality Assessment process · Vice Rector for Quality Assurance
Other Vice-Rectors Involved	-
Other Structures Involved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · PoliTO Strategies Study Center · Centre for Gender Studies · STARQ Office in staff to the Director General - Strategy, Analysis, Reporting and Quality · WGs PoliTO CoARA
Polito in transition (Rector's Programme)	<p>Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Enhancement of research environments · Strengthening of research support · Promotion of internationally oriented research <p>Actions: 69, 75, 86, 107, 108, 121</p>
Strategic Plan TAGs	International University
University Action Plan TAGs - Areas of Intervention	Enhancement of the vocations of researchers and teaching staff
Outcome of the Action	<p>The Action is linked to the framework defined by the University's Open Access Policy (Art. 10), which provides for the possibility of introducing incentives in internal evaluation processes to promote the adoption of open science principles by research staff affiliated with the Polytechnic.</p> <p>The Policy also envisages the experimentation of integrated research assessment criteria, both qualitative and quantitative, as well as the use of alternative bibliometric and webometric indicators based on open access contributions.</p> <p>These elements constitute an institutional basis for the progressive alignment of evaluation criteria with the principles of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment and the recommendations of CoARA.</p>

Supporting CoARA Commitment: 7. Raise awareness of research assessment reform and provide transparent communication, guidance, and training on assessment criteria and processes as well as their use

Action	A.5 Presentation of CoARA initiatives and progress, as well as of the University's Action Plan, to governance bodies and the academic community
Timeline	2024-2027 (periodic schedule)
Indicators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · 1 annual presentation to the relevant bodies (PQA, CARTT, Academic Senate) · 1 annual workshop open to the entire academic community
Responsibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Open Science Study Centre · Vice Rector for PoliTo Strategic Plan
Other Vice-Rectors Involved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Vice Rector for Human and Economic Resources · Vice Rector for Internal Affairs · Vice Rector for Quality Assurance
Other Structures Involved	WG PoliTO CoARA
Polito in transition (Rector's Programme)	<p>Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Enhancement of internal training · Strengthening of participation and sharing <p>Actions: 95, 53, 54, 105, 110, 132</p>
Strategic Plan TAGs	A recognizable and acknowledged University
University Action Plan TAGs - Areas of Intervention	Internal Communication
Outcome of the Action	<p>The Action aimed at the structured and progressive sharing of the CoARA Action Plan and its progress with the University's governance bodies and the academic community, in order to ensure transparency, strategic alignment, and full integration of the document into institutional processes.</p> <p>During 2024, the CoARA Action Plan was presented to the University Quality Board (PQA): in the session of 12 September 2024, the document was shared to collect any comments and suggestions, while in the meeting of 5 November 2024, the PQA issued a favorable opinion. Subsequently, the document followed the approval process within the central governing bodies, receiving the Academic Senate's endorsement on 21 January 2025 and the approval of the Board of Directors on 30 January 2025.</p> <p>Following this process, the CoARA Action Plan was formally attached to the University's Integrated Activity and Organization Plan (PIAO) and was aligned with the objectives and actions of the new University Strategic Plan, strengthening its role as a tool for guiding and coordinating research assessment policies.</p> <p>As part of dissemination activities and engagement with the academic community, a seminar dedicated to the CoARA Action Plan was also organized, delivered by Francesca Di Donato (CNR), member of the G7 Open Science working group and co-chair of the Italian National Chapter of CoARA. The seminar took place on 21 March 2025 at the Politecnico di Torino and was addressed to both governance and the academic community, aiming to raise awareness of CoARA principles and the actions foreseen in the Action Plan. The meeting materials (slides and recording) were made openly available to support broad dissemination of the content (https://zenodo.org/records/15058489). The Action Plan was also presented to the University Open Access Committee.</p>

Supporting CoARA Commitment: 7. Raise awareness of research assessment reform and provide transparent communication, guidance, and training on assessment criteria and processes as well as their use

Action	A.6 Creation and periodic updating of a section on the University website dedicated to the dissemination of CoARA initiatives and the implementation of the internal roadmap
Timeline	2025-2027 (periodic schedule)
Indicators	Creation of the dedicated section within the PoliTO website.
Responsibility	ARIA Department - Institutional Relations, General Affairs, Archives and Libraries
Other Vice-Rectors Involved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Open Science Study Centre · Vice Rector for PoliTo Communication and Promotion
Other Structures Involved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · PoliTO Strategies Study Center · STARQ Office in staff to the Director General - Strategy, Analysis, Reporting and Quality
Polito in transition (Rector's Programme)	<p>Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Enhancement of internal training · Strengthening of participation and sharing <p>Actions: 95, 53, 54, 105, 110, 132</p>
Strategic Plan TAGs	A recognizable and acknowledged University
University Action Plan TAGs - Areas of Intervention	Internal Communication
Outcome of the Action	<p>A <u>dedicated CoARA section</u> has been created on the University website, designed as an institutional information space for the dissemination of initiatives related to the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment and to support the implementation of the internal roadmap of the Politecnico di Torino.</p> <p>The section introduces the Coalition's reference context, illustrating its objectives, founding principles, and organizational structure, with particular attention to the commitments outlined in the Agreement, the Working Groups, and the National Chapters. Within this framework, the role of the Politecnico di Torino in CoARA is made explicit, including participation in thematic Working Groups and coordination of the Italian National Chapter's Task Force 2.3, dedicated to awareness and training activities.</p> <p>A specific area is devoted to the University's path of adherence to CoARA and the related Action Plan, highlighting its integration into the institutional strategy and alignment with the University Strategic Plan, the European Charter for Researchers, and the European Commission guidelines.</p> <p>Finally, the section includes a "Resources and Further Reading" area, which gathers links to official documents, reference materials, institutional websites, and project outputs (Action Plan, ARRA, National Chapter resources, and FEDRA project materials), and is periodically updated to support information and dissemination activities aimed at the academic community.</p>

Supporting CoARA Commitment: 7. Raise awareness of research assessment reform and provide transparent communication, guidance, and training on assessment criteria and processes as well as their use

Action	A.7 Training on the use of thematic dashboards (in particular the Publications Dashboard) and tools supporting research assessment
Timeline	2025-2027 (periodic schedule)
Indicators	-
Responsibility	PoliTO Strategies Study Center
Other Vice-Rectors Involved	-
Other Structures Involved	STARQ Office in staff to the Director General - Strategy, Analysis, Reporting and Quality
Polito in transition (Rector's Programme)	Objectives: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Enhancement of internal training · Strengthening of participation and sharing Actions: 95, 53, 54, 105, 110, 132
Strategic Plan TAGs	A recognizable and acknowledged University
University Action Plan TAGs - Areas of Intervention	Information and decision-support services, transparency, and accessibility of institutional information.
Outcome of the Action	<p>Within the scope of the Action, presentation and training activities were conducted on the University's thematic dashboards, developed by the PoliTO Strategies Study Center as tools to support decision-making, monitoring, and research assessment. This is an integrated dashboard system developed by the PoliTO Strategies Study Center (formerly CentroStudi4IMPACT@POLITO) and the STARQ Area – Strategy, Analysis, Reporting, and Quality (formerly PROSIQ and PEPS Directorates) to support the definition, implementation, and monitoring of strategic planning activities. The dashboards were presented to the Departments during the kick-off meeting of the Departmental Strategic Planning process (20 March 2025), to support the definition, implementation, and review of departmental strategies.</p> <p>In a separate initiative, on 15 October 2025, an onboarding meeting was organized for newly hired researchers (RTD, RTT, and research fellows), specifically dedicated to the presentation of the Publications Dashboard as a tool for monitoring scientific output.</p>

Supporting CoARA Commitment: 7. Raise awareness of research assessment reform and provide transparent communication, guidance, and training on assessment criteria and processes as well as their use

Action	A.8 Preparation of informational material on the conscious and responsible use of indicators to support research assessment;
Timeline	2025
Indicators	-
Responsibility	WG PolITO CoARA
Other Vice-Rectors Involved	Vice Rector for Internal Affairs
Other Structures Involved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Open Science Study Centre · PoliTO Strategies Study Center · STARQ Office in staff to the Director General - Strategy, Analysis, Reporting and Quality · ARIA Department - Institutional Relations, General Affairs, Archives and Libraries · MultiMedia Hub
Polito in transition (Rector's Programme)	<p>Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Enhancement of internal training · Strengthening of participation and sharing <p>Actions: 95, 53, 54, 105, 110, 132</p>
Strategic Plan TAGs	International University
University Action Plan TAGs - Areas of Intervention	Training of teaching staff
Outcome of the Action	<p>In connection with Action A.1, training and support initiatives were launched for the academic community and members of selection committees, aimed at promoting the adoption of broader assessment approaches within recruitment and career progression processes.</p> <p>These activities are part of the broader effort to prepare informational materials for the committees and to strengthen institutional awareness regarding the contextualized use of quantitative indicators in the University's evaluation processes.</p>

Supporting CoARA Commitment: 7. Raise awareness of research assessment reform and provide transparent communication, guidance, and training on assessment criteria and processes as well as their use

Action	A.9 Actions aimed at increasing the use of the University repository IRIS (publications and datasets).
Timeline	2025-2027 (as needed)
Indicators	-
Responsibility	ARIA Department - Institutional Relations, General Affairs, Archives and Libraries
Other Vice-Rectors Involved	-
Other Structures Involved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Open Science Study Centre · GdL Open Access · Open Access Board
Polito in transition (Rector's Programme)	<p>Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Enhancement of internal training · Strengthening of participation and sharing <p>Actions: 95, 53, 54, 105, 110, 132</p>
Strategic Plan TAGs	University as a driver of competitiveness
University Action Plan TAGs - Areas of Intervention	Support for research project development
Outcome of the Action	<p>Between October 2024 and February 2025, a presentation of the University's Open Science policies (open access and research data management) was conducted in each of the 11 Department Councils, raising awareness on the use of the University repository Porto@IRIS for uploading publications and metadata (authors, title, DOI) related to datasets and other research outputs. This involves depositing metadata in section 9.FAIR DATA COLLECTION or indicating the dataset DOI in the publication record to which it is linked, if applicable. Currently, 60 items are present in section 9 of Porto@IRIS—still a small number—but uploads increased by +150% in 2024/2025 compared to the total of previous years (2019–2023).</p> <p>The functioning of Porto@IRIS is also covered in the doctoral Soft Skills course "Research Data Management and Open Science" and in the "Open Science Starter Kit" seminars aimed at the entire Politecnico community. Further informational actions through the University Open Access Board representatives and targeted communications to faculty and research staff will be implemented in 2026.</p> <p>To strengthen the University's information system, activities have been carried out to enhance the IRIS Resources Management (RM) module, starting with the revision and upgrading of the research staff profile, aimed at mapping and making more visible the skills, experiences, and areas of activity of researchers. On this basis, functionalities for managing research groups were subsequently developed, with the goal of representing scientific collaborations and internal organizational dynamics in a more structured way.</p> <p>In a further phase, activities focused on the Knowledge Valorization module, addressing third mission dimensions and social impact, contributing to making transfer, dissemination, and societal engagement activities traceable and recognizable. Overall, these interventions have strengthened the quality and updating of information on professional and scientific paths of staff, improved the visibility of skills present at the University, and supported more integrated practices for planning, monitoring, and valorizing research activities.</p>

Supporting CoARA Commitment: 7. Raise awareness of research assessment reform and provide transparent communication, guidance, and training on assessment criteria and processes as well as their use

Action	A.10 Training activities on best practices in scientific publishing and peer review
Timeline	2025
Indicators	-
Responsibility	ARIA Department - Institutional Relations, General Affairs, Archives and Libraries
Other Vice-Rectors Involved	Open Science Study Centre
Other Structures Involved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Open Access Board di Ateneo · WG PoliT0 CoARA
Polito in transition (Rector's Programme)	<p>Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Enhancement of internal training · Strengthening of participation and sharing <p>Actions: 95, 53, 54, 105, 110, 132</p>
Strategic Plan TAGs	International University
University Action Plan TAGs - Areas of Intervention	Training of teaching staff
Outcome of the Action	<p>Within the scope of this Action, the Politecnico di Torino contributed to the training activities coordinated by Task 2.3 "Awareness and Training" of the CoARA National Chapter, which it coordinates. In particular, two seminars were organized in 2025:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 18 June 2025 – New editorial and peer review models inspired by open science principles, focused on editorial and peer review models inspired by Open Science principles (recordings and materials available); • 9 July 2025 – Open resources for research monitoring and assessment, focused on the use of open resources and tools to support research assessment (recordings and materials available). <p>These initiatives contributed to the dissemination of responsible and innovative practices in scientific communication and peer review processes, in line with CoARA principles.</p>

Supporting CoARA Commitment: 7. Raise awareness of research assessment reform and provide transparent communication, guidance, and training on assessment criteria and processes as well as their use

Action	A.11 Strengthening training and information activities related to research data management according to FAIR principles and promoting Open Science practices.
Timeline	2025-2027 (periodic schedule)
Indicators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Open Science Starter Kit” seminars, 2-hour sessions, on Open Science and research data management according to FAIR principles. Two editions per year aimed at all researchers. · Series of short videos on Open Science · Series of podcasts on Open Science
Responsibility	ARIA Department - Institutional Relations, General Affairs, Archives and Libraries (Domain Expert Open Science)
Other Vice-Rectors Involved	Open Science Study Centre
Other Structures Involved	-
Polito in transition (Rector's Programme)	<p>Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Enhancement of internal training · Strengthening of participation and sharing <p>Actions: 95, 53, 54, 105, 110, 132</p>
Strategic Plan TAGs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · International University · University as a driver of competitiveness
University Action Plan TAGs - Areas of Intervention	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Enhancement of the vocations of researchers and teaching staff · Training of teaching staff
Outcome of the Action	<p>The first edition of the “Open Science Starter Kit” seminar was held on 23 October 2025, and a second edition is scheduled for May 2026. The two-hour seminar, delivered in Italian, was attended by 37 participants. The seminar was recorded, and the recording will be uploaded to the training portal for on-demand access.</p> <p>Within the EDVANCE project, two one-hour MOOCs are being produced in a bilingual ITA/EN format, covering Open Science and FAIR data, with one focused on STEM disciplines and the other on the humanities.</p> <p>On 5 February 2025, the presentation of the book “Open Science: European Policies for a New Research Paradigm”, published by Mimesis Edizioni and authored by Ludovica Paseri, research fellow in Philosophy of Law and Legal Informatics at the Department of Law, University of Turin, and fellow at the Nexa Center for Internet & Society at Politecnico di Torino, took place.</p> <p>On 21 May 2025, the seminar “How can researchers leverage Open Source AI with a data-centric approach” was delivered by Dr. Shalini Kurapati, Clearbox AI. https://www.polito.it/ateneo/comunicazione-ufficio-stampa/appuntamenti/news?idn=25859</p> <p>On 14 October 2025, the workshop “FAIR Implementation Profile (FIP)”, from 10:00 to 15:30, was conducted by Dr. Andrea Tarallo, CNR, certified instructor by the GO FAIR Foundation.</p> <p>Seminar materials (slides and/or recordings) are available at: https://www.polito.it/impatto-sociale/biblioteche-di-ateneo/scienza-aperta/convegni-seminari-e-progetti-di-ateneo.</p>

Supporting CoARA Commitment: 7. Raise awareness of research assessment reform and provide transparent communication, guidance, and training on assessment criteria and processes as well as their use

Action	<p>A.12 Strengthening support for research staff to encourage, across different disciplinary areas, the adoption of Open Science methodologies and practices throughout the research project lifecycle, including support for researchers’ diamond open access publishing initiatives.</p>
Timeline	2025-2027
Indicators	-
Responsibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Vice Rector for Scientific and Technological Innovation · Vice Rector for Society and Public Engagement, Community, and Rector’s Program Implementation · Vice Rector for PoliTo Communication and Promotion
Other Vice-Rectors Involved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Vice Rector for Human and Economic Resources · Open Science Study Centre
Other Structures Involved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · RIMIN Department - Research, Technology Transfer and Innovation · ARIA Department - Institutional Relations, General Affairs, Archives and Libraries · STARQ Office in staff to the Director General - Strategy, Analysis, Reporting and Quality
Politointransition (Rector’s Programme)	<p>Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Enhancement of internal training · Strengthening of participation and sharing <p>Actions: 95, 53, 54, 105, 110, 132</p>
Strategic Plan TAGs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · A recognizable and acknowledged University
University Action Plan TAGs - Areas of Intervention	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Support for research project development · Training of teaching staff
Outcome of the Action	<p>A post-doctoral research fellow (AdR) position was renewed, focused on Open Science in the humanities, to develop best practices and methodologies supporting the entire academic community.</p>

Supporting CoARA Commitment: 8. Exchange practices and experiences to enable mutual learning within and beyond the Coalition

Action	<p>A.13</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Participation in the activities of the National Chapter; · Coordination of Task 2.3 “Awareness and Training”; · Participation in the activities of Tasks 1.1, 1.2.2, 1.3, and Work Package 3;
Timeline	Ongoing
Indicators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · 2 training seminars per year organized by T2.3; materials made available as Open Educational Resources (OER); · Contribution to the deliverables of the Tasks/Work Packages.
Responsibility	Open Science Study Centre
Other Vice-Rectors Involved	-
Other Structures Involved	WG PoliT0 CoARA
Polito in transition (Rector’s Programme)	<p>Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Public engagement and increased societal involvement · Building and promoting a recognizable identity for the University · Strengthening of participation and sharing · Care and enhancement of staff <p>Actions: 76, 78, 134</p>
Strategic Plan TAGs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · A recognizable and acknowledged University · University as a driver of competitiveness
University Action Plan TAGs - Areas of Intervention	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Quality Assurance; · Equal opportunity policies in staff career development · Support for policy and decision-making at local, national, and European levels · Enhancement of the vocations of researchers and teaching staff
Outcome of the Action	<p>The Politecnico di Torino actively participated in the activities of the Italian National Chapter of CoARA, taking on the coordination of Task 2.3 “Awareness and Training” and contributing to Tasks 1.1, 1.2.2, 1.3, and Work Package 3. Between September 2023 and July 2025, within Task 2.3, three online training seminars were organized to strengthen institutional awareness, promote the exchange of best practices, and develop skills on topics related to the reform of research assessment. The materials produced were made available as Open Educational Resources via Zenodo.</p> <p>The Politecnico di Torino also took part in the in-person event held in Pisa on 13 November 2025, marking the conclusion of the first call of the National Chapter.</p>

Supporting CoARA Commitment: 8. Exchange practices and experiences to enable mutual learning within and beyond the Coalition

Action	<p>A.14 Participation in the activities of the CoARA Working Groups:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Experiments in Assessment – Idea generation, co-creation, and piloting • TIER - Towards an Inclusive Evaluation of Research
Timeline	Ongoing
Indicators	Contribution to the deliverables of the WGs
Responsibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Open Science Study Centre · Centre for Gender Studies
Other Vice-Rectors Involved	-
Other Structures Involved	WG PoliTO CoARA
Politointransition (Rector's Programme)	<p>Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Public engagement and increased societal involvement · Building and promoting a recognizable identity for the University · Strengthening of participation and sharing · Care and enhancement of staff <p>Actions: 76, 78, 134</p>
Strategic Plan TAGs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · International University · A recognizable and acknowledged University
University Action Plan TAGs - Areas of Intervention	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · External visibility within and beyond the EU · Equal opportunity policies in staff career development · Support for policy and decision-making at local, national, and European levels · Enhancement of the vocations of researchers and teaching staff
Outcome of the Action	<p>Within the framework of the initiative, the Politecnico di Torino participates in the activities of the CoARA Working Group “Experiments in Assessment – Idea generation, co-creation, and piloting”, contributing to the development of the group’s deliverables. The WG EiA focuses on the collection, analysis, and structuring of experiences and experiments related to research assessment reform, with the aim of producing operational tools to support institutions. Between 2023 and 2025, the group conducted an international survey (with over 85 responses), organized thematic workshops, and initiated a systematic literature review on research assessment experiments. The current activity is focused on the development of an online catalogue of ideas for assessment experiments, conceived as an open and dynamic resource for the CoARA community, featuring structured entries, links to the literature, and operational guidance. In 2025, the WG obtained a 12-month extension to complete the development of the catalogue, which will represent the group’s main output, accompanied by a methodological white paper and a public launch webinar.</p> <p>In addition, the Politecnico di Torino participates in the WG TIER (Towards an Inclusive Evaluation of Research), which aims to promote a more inclusive and bias-free research evaluation, both in academic recruitment (RPOs) and in the evaluation of research projects (RFOs). The project is based on international comparative analyses and on a survey on the perception of bias, which collected over 1,700 responses across the participating institutions. Among the main results achieved are: the identification of critical issues and good practices in evaluation processes; the production of training materials (videos) for gender bias awareness; a report on the mid-term meeting held at the University of Milano-Bicocca (7 February 2025); and a workshop held in July 2025 with other CoARA WGs on “Inclusive Excellence”. The WG obtained a 12-month extension in 2025 to develop a self-assessment toolkit on inclusive evaluation for universities and research institutions, and to present the toolkit through a dissemination tour across participating organizations. CoARA TIER on LinkedIn</p>

Supporting CoARA Commitment: 8. Exchange practices and experiences to enable mutual learning within and beyond the Coalition

Action	A.15 Dissemination and exchange of best practices within international networks, alliances, and initiatives (UNITE!, CESAER, Magalhães Network, EUA...)
Timeline	Ongoing
Indicators	Co-organization or participation as speakers in at least one seminar per year
Responsibility	WG PolITO CoARA
Other Vice-Rectors Involved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Vice Rector for International Affairs · Rector's Senior Advisor for International University Networks and the European University Alliance Unite!
Other Structures Involved	-
Polito in transition (Rector's Programme)	<p>Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Public engagement and increased societal involvement · Building and promoting a recognizable identity for the University · Strengthening of participation and sharing · Care and enhancement of staff <p>Actions: 76, 78, 134</p>
Strategic Plan TAGs	International University;
University Action Plan TAGs - Areas of Intervention	External visibility within and beyond the EU
Outcome of the Action	<p>The Politecnico di Torino contributed to the dissemination and exchange of best practices on research assessment reform by participating in initiatives within international networks and alliances. In particular, the University presented its implementation process of CoARA principles and the institutional Action Plan during the event <i>"Implementing CoARA's Principles at Polytechnic University of Turin"</i>, held on 11 October 2024 at the Wrocław University of Science and Technology and organized by the UNITE! alliance (https://zenodo.org/records/15657807), as well as at the <i>"CESAER Workshop on COARA Implementation"</i>, held on 15 May 2025 (https://zenodo.org/records/15657878). These interventions facilitated exchanges among institutions on approaches and operational tools for implementing CoARA principles.</p>

Supporting CoARA Commitment: 9. Communicate progress made on adherence to the Principles and implementation of the Commitments

Action	A.16 Publication of the Roadmap and its updates. (See also actions A6 and A19)
Timeline	2024-2027 (periodic schedule)
Indicators	-
Responsibility	WG PoliTO CoARA
Other Vice-Rectors Involved	Vice Rector for PoliTo Communication and Promotion
Other Structures Involved	-
Polito in transition (Rector's Programme)	Objectives: · Strengthening of participation and sharing Actions: 95, 53, 105, 131, 132
Strategic Plan TAGs	A recognizable and acknowledged University
University Action Plan TAGs - Areas of Intervention	Internal Communication
Outcome of the Action	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Roadmap published on 14/03/2025 (https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15023889) • Update published on 16/04/2026, following its presentation and discussion at the Academic Quality Assurance Committee (PQA) meeting held on 20/03/2026.

Supporting CoARA Commitment: 10. Evaluate practices, criteria and tools based on solid evidence and the state-of-the-art in research on research, and make data openly available for evidence gathering and research

Action	A.17 Enhancement of the Public Research Registry with a focus on interoperability and inclusion, and valorization of Open Science outputs (datasets, software, etc.)
Timeline	2025-2027
Indicators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentation of a project within CoARA Boost • Analysis report of the current architecture and design of necessary updates
Responsibility	WG PolITO CoARA
Other Vice-Rectors Involved	Vice Rector for Scientific and Technological Innovation
Other Structures Involved	-
Polito in transition (Rector's Programme)	<p>Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhancement of research environments • Strengthening of research support • Promotion of internationally oriented research • Care and enhancement of staff <p>Actions: 57, 134, 86</p>
Strategic Plan TAGs	University as a driver of competitiveness
University Action Plan TAGs - Areas of Intervention	Promotion of the research outcomes of the Politecnico
Outcome of the Action	<p>The FEDRA project – <i>An institutional FAIR data lake for transparent, inclusive, and reproducible Research Assessment</i>, developed in collaboration between the Open Science Study Centre, GEDI, and University Strategy, was awarded CoARA Boost funding for the implementation of an internal data lake adhering to FAIR principles (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable).</p> <p>The project ran from February 2025 to January 2026. Activities included analyzing the current structure of the Research Registry, designing its development from a data lake perspective, and developing metadata testing routines from open research data platforms, useful for feeding the data lake in the future.</p> <p>See: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15756131; https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18434865.</p>

Supporting CoARA Commitment: 10. Evaluate practices, criteria and tools based on solid evidence and the state-of-the-art in research on research, and make data openly available for evidence gathering and research

Action	A.18 Implementation of a monitoring system for publications and Open Access outputs and Open Science activities (OS Dashboard), also using open databases.
Timeline	2027
Indicators	-
Responsibility	STARQ Office in staff to the Director General - Strategy, Analysis, Reporting and Quality
Other Vice-Rectors Involved	Open Science Study Centre
Other Structures Involved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Gdl Open Access · Open Access Board · ARIA Department - Institutional Relations, General Affairs, Archives and Libraries · PoliTO Strategies Study Center
Polito in transition (Rector's Programme)	<p>Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Enhancement of research environments · Strengthening of research support · Promotion of internationally oriented research · Care and enhancement of staff <p>Actions: 57, 134, 86</p>
Strategic Plan TAGs	A recognizable and acknowledged University
University Action Plan TAGs - Areas of Intervention	Information and decision-support services, transparency, and accessibility of institutional information
Outcome of the Action	<p>The activity (see also Action A17) included a feasibility study on the use of open databases, in particular OpenAlex, to enhance the monitoring of publications and Open Science outputs. The results are analyzed in https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18434865 and highlight the potential informational enrichment made possible by using open databases in addition to commercial databases (SCOPUS) alone.</p> <p>As a demonstrator, a prototype dashboard was created that maps the collaborations of the Politecnico di Torino based on datasets available on OpenAlex: https://jnfrdm.github.io/polito_collaborations_dashboard/. Following this research activity, discussions were initiated with OpenAIRE and other Italian universities aimed at implementing institutional dashboards and a national Open Science dashboard.</p>

Supporting CoARA Commitment: 10. Evaluate practices, criteria and tools based on solid evidence and the state-of-the-art in research on research, and make data openly available for evidence gathering and research

Action	A.19 Preparation of an institutional report on Open Science
Timeline	2025 – 2027 (annual)
Indicators	-
Responsibility	Open Science Study Centre
Other Vice-Rectors Involved	-
Other Structures Involved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · PoliTO WG on Open Access · Open Access Board · ARIA Department - Institutional Relations, General Affairs, Archives and Libraries · STARQ Office in staff to the Director General - Strategy, Analysis, Reporting and Quality · PoliTO Strategies Study Center
Polito in transition (Rector's Programme)	<p>Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Enhancement of research environments · Strengthening of research support · Promotion of internationally oriented research · Care and enhancement of staff <p>Actions: 57, 134, 86</p>
Strategic Plan TAGs	A recognizable and acknowledged University
University Action Plan TAGs - Areas of Intervention	Information and decision-support services, transparency, and accessibility of institutional information
Outcome of the Action	N/A. Scheduled for 2026.